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AN ASSESSMENT ON THE ADEQUACY OF PERSONAL INCOME TAX ACT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Personal Income Tax (PIT) calculated on a graduated scale is considered one of the more progressive taxes in common use. For a tax that directly affects the amount of income that individuals can keep, it is imperative to ensure that taxation is designed fairly. A flat rate PIT is likely to result in richer taxpayers, who have a greater ability to pay, contributing relatively less than those with less ability to pay. While the risk of regressive outcomes from a flat rate may be at least partially mitigated by introducing allowances and deductions for low-income earners, the risk of wealthy individuals contributing disproportionately small amounts remains. Policymakers may opt to exempt certain amounts of income from tax, this will eventually create an unjust system, where the wealthy pay less. The existing law PITA needs to close the gap and create a fair treatment irrespective of economic status of taxpayers, especially income tax collected through payroll deductions which may work against those whose income is irregular, informal or unrecognised. This can be done through legislation by amending the existing PITA to prevent higher income earners from access to exemptions and to make them contribute proportionately more tax. The aim of this paper is to look into the personal income tax law of Nigeria and consider the above challenges and recommend appropriately.

Keywords: Taxation, Taxable person, Taxpayer and income tax.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Personal Income Tax (PIT) according to Decree No.4 of 1993 is a tax imposed on the incomes of individuals, communities and families.¹ It is also charged on the incomes due to a trustee or an estate.² Since the enforcement of personal income tax through Decree No.4 of 1993, amendments have been made to this decree almost on 10year basis all in the effort to overcome challenges that are identified with the actualisation of the objectives of the tax regime.³

Personal income refers to income of individuals, families or communities arising from employment, business, trade, profession, or vocation.⁴ Personal Income Tax (PIT) (Amendment) Act 2011 defines personal income tax as the tax imposed by the government on the incomes of individuals and corporation soles.⁵ This tax is levied on individuals, body of individuals or corporation soles based on their level of income or profits.⁶

This is a tax that is imposed on individuals who are either in employment or running their own small businesses under a business name or partnership.⁷ Under the law, Federal and State ‘tax boards are empowered to identify persons living in or earning income from Nigeria who are required to pay tax, and assess incomes and tax their incomes using specified guideline and rules.’⁸ The law also guides the tax official in identifying the residence of potential tax payers, as well as the sources and origins of their incomes for the purpose of taxing the income.⁹

The wording of the charging provision of PITA clearly made no provision nor alluded to profits or gain realised from e-commerce.¹⁰ Since the Act was made before e-commerce came on board, it can be argued that gain/ profits made from any trade or business not being that contemplated in the Act should not be subjected to tax.¹¹ The Finance Act although made

1 Akhidime E. Augustine and Abusonwan E. Rachel, ‘Nigeria Personal Income Tax (Amendment) Act 2011: Implications for Tax Administration and Enforcement’(2013)2(4)IJAH<
<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ijah/article/view/106711> > accessed 14 August 2020.

2 Ibid

3 Ibid

4 Adeusi Amos Sunday, Uniamikogbo Emmanuel and Erah Ose Dominic, ‘Non-Oil Revenue and Economic Growth in Nigeria’(2020)11(8)RJFA<
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Uniamikogbo_Emmanuel/publication/341250809 > accessed 14 August 2020.

5 Ibid

6 Ibid

7 Ekeocha Patterson Chukwuemeka and others (n. 26).

8 Ibid

9 Ibid

10 Meshach N Umenweke and Ginikachi Nkem Onyenukporo, (n. 80)

11 Ibid

changes to PITA, none relates to revenue generated by individuals through e-commerce.¹² This notwithstanding, gains or profits made in trade or business by an individual whether traditional trade methods or through e-commerce is still subject to personal income tax.¹³

The Personal Income Tax Act Cap P8, LFN 2004, is now amended by the Personal Income Tax (amendment) Act, 2011.¹⁴ This follows many years of agitation for the Personal Income Tax Law in Nigeria to be brought in line with present day economic realities, and also to increase the compliance levels and the amount of tax voluntarily paid and or collected by the Nigerian government.¹⁵

Personal Income Tax (PIT) can be defined as a tax that is imposed on the income of “persons”, that is, an individual who is either in paid employment or self-employed.¹⁶ Personal income tax can be viewed as a compulsory levy paid by individuals that are self-employed or in gainful employment in either public or private organizations to the government.¹⁷

2.0. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The legal regime regarding Personal Income Tax (PIT) to an extent has remained unsatisfactory, and problematic to taxpayers. This is in spite of the fact that tax reform has of recent been a key element in economic reform which the country had undergone. It is therefore felt that personal Income tax in Nigeria requires radical handling to ensure that a large number of the taxable population do not escape tax.

In as much as the reach will continue to enjoy tax break, the low-income earners and the economy at large will bear the ultimate consequences, especially in an ear of economic downturn. The Act needs to eliminate all inceptives to high income earners so that all taxpayers will pay its fair share, and consider those vulnerable taxpayers who don't have regular income.

12 Ibid

13 Ibid

14 Zainab Dabo, Aimuyedo Mary and Muhammad Tanko, ‘The Effect of Personal Income Tax Amendment Act on Revenue Generation in Nigeria’(2014)< https://papers.ssrn.com/so13/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2488098 > accessed 14 August 2020.

15 Ibid

16 Aronmwan Edosa Joshua, Imobhio Ehichioya and Izedonmi Famous, ‘Determinants of Personal Income Tax Compliance: Perception of Nigerian Taxpayers’(2015)<

https://papers.ssrn.com/so13/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2619855 > accessed 14 August 2020.

17 Ibid

3.0. PERSONS ON WHOM TAX IS TO BE COLLECTED

Tax of an amount to be determined from the Table set out in the Sixth Schedule (in this Act referred to as —income tax) shall be payable for each year of assessment on the total income of-

(a) every individual other than persons covered under paragraph (b) of this subsection or corporation sole or body of individuals deemed to be resident for that year in the relevant State under the provisions of this Act; and

(b) the following other persons, that is-

(i) persons employed in the Nigerian Army, the Nigerian Navy, the Nigerian Air Force, the Nigerian Police Force other than in a civilian capacity;

(ii) officers of the Nigerian Foreign Service;

(iii) every resident of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja; and

(iv) a person resident outside Nigeria who derives income or profit from Nigeria.¹⁸

Notwithstanding anything in the principal Act, the relevant tax authority in a State shall have powers to collect tax under this Act from itinerant workers.¹⁹

3.1 INDIVIDUALS OTHER THAN ITINERANT WORKERS

In the case of an individual, other than an itinerant worker and persons covered under paragraph (b) of subsection (1) of section 2, tax for any year of assessment may be collected only by the State in which the individual is deemed to be resident for that year under the provisions of the First Schedule to this Act and in the case of persons referred to in subsection (1) (b) of this section, tax shall be collected by the Federal Board of Inland Revenue.²⁰

3.2 ITINERANT WORKERS

In the case of an itinerant worker, tax may be collected for any year by any State in which the itinerant worker is found during the year:

18 Section 2 (1) Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) Cap. P8 LFN 2004

19 Proviso (1A) to Section 2 Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) LFN 2004

20 Section 2 (2) PITA Supra

Provided that:

(a) in an assessment for any year upon an itinerant worker, credit shall be given against the tax payable, but not exceeding the amount thereof, for any income tax already paid by him to any other tax authority for the same year; and

(b) collection of so much of any tax imposed in a territory on an itinerant worker for a year of assessment as remains unpaid on the itinerant worker leaving that territory during that year shall remain in abeyance during his absence from that territory, and if he returns to that territory having during his absence paid tax in some other territory for that year, credit shall be given against any unpaid tax in the first- mentioned territory, but not exceeding that unpaid amount, for the tax paid in that other territory.²¹

4.0. INCOME CHARGEABLE

Subject to the provisions of this Act, tax shall be payable for each year of assessment on the aggregate amounts each of which is the income of every taxable person, for the year, from a source inside or outside Nigeria, including, without restricting the generality of the foregoing-

(a) gain or profit from any trade, business, profession or vocation, for whatever period of time such trade, business, profession or vocation may have been carried on or exercised;

(b) any salary, wage, fee, allowance or other gain or profit from employment including compensations, bonuses, premiums, benefits or other perquisites allowed, given or granted by any person to any temporary or permanent employee other than so much of any sums as or expenses incurred by him in the performance of his duties, and from which it is not intended that the employee should make any profit or gain;

(i) medical or dental expenses incurred by the employee;

(ii) the cost of any passage to or from Nigeria incurred by the employee;

(iii) any sum paid in respect of the maintenance or education of a child if any provision of this Act provides that any sum received by the employee during a year of assessment shall be deducted from the personal reliefs to be granted to him for the next following year;

²¹ Section 2 (3) PITA Supra

(iv) so much of any amount of rent the employee is treated as being in receipt equal to the annual amount deemed to be incurred by the employer under section 4 of this Act;

(v) so much of any amount of rent the employee is treated as having received under the provisions of section 5 of this Act;

(vi) so much of the amount of rent subsidy or rent allowance paid by the employer, to or on account, for the employee not exceeding N100,000 per annum;

(vii) meal subsidy or meal allowance, subject to a maximum of N5,000 per annum;

(viii) utility allowance of N 10,000 per annum;

(ix) entertainment allowance of N6,000 per annum;

(x) leave grant, subject to a maximum of ten per cent of annual basic salary;

(c) gain or profit including any premiums arising from a right granted to any other person for the use or occupation of any property;

(d) dividend, interest or discount;

(e) any pension, charge or annuity;

(f) any profit, gain or other payment not falling within paragraphs (a) to (e) inclusive of this subsection.²²

5.0. BUSINESS OR TRADE ONLY PARTIALLY CARRIED ON OR DEEMED TO BE CARRIED ON IN NIGERIA

Where an individual, an executor, or a trustee, outside Nigeria carries on a trade or business of which only part of the operations is carried out in Nigeria, the gains or profits of the trade or business shall be deemed to be derived from Nigeria to the extent to which such gains or profits are not attributable to that part of the operations carried on outside Nigeria.²³

Provided that-

(a) the individual, executor or trustee does not have a fixed base in Nigeria from which

²² Section 3 (1) PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

²³ Section 6 PITA Supra

he carries on such trade or business;

(b) the individual, executor or trustee does not habitually operate a trade or business

through a person in Nigeria authorised to conclude contracts on his behalf or on behalf of some other persons related to him or both of whom are controlled by some other person or does not habitually maintain a stock of goods or merchandise in Nigeria from which deliveries are regularly made on his behalf;

(c) the trade or business in Nigeria does not involve a single contract for surveys, deliveries, installations or construction;

(d) the trade or business is not between persons both of whom are controlled by some other person and such that conditions are made or imposed between such persons in their commercial or financial relations which in the opinion of the relevant tax authority is deemed to be artificial or fictitious.²⁴

6.0. RELEVANT TAX AUTHORITY MAY ASSESS AND CHARGE TAX ON THE TURNOVER OF A BUSINESS

Where, in respect of any business carried on by a person it appears to the relevant tax authority that for any year of assessment, the business produces either no assessable income or an assessable income which in the opinion of the relevant tax authority is less than might be expected to arise from that business or, as the case may be, the true amount of the assessable income of that person from the business cannot be readily ascertained, the relevant tax authority may for that year of assessment, in respect of that business, and notwithstanding any other provision of this Act²⁵

(a) if the whole of the operations of the business are carried on in Nigeria, assess and charge the person carrying on the business on such fair and reasonable percentage of the turnover of the business, as the relevant tax authority may determine;

(b) if that person is a non-resident who-

(i) has a fixed base from where he carried on such business, assess and charge that person on such a fair and reasonable percentage of the turnover attributable to that fixed base;

²⁴ Section 6 (a-d) PITA Cap P8 LFN 2004
²⁵ Section 7 PITA Supra

(ii) operates a business through a person authorised to conclude contracts on his behalf or on behalf of some person related to him or both of whom are controlled by some other person or operates a business through a person who regularly makes deliveries from a stock of goods or merchandise habitually held in Nigeria on his behalf, assess and charge that person on a fair and reasonable percentage of the turnover of the business carried on through that person;

(iii) operates a business in Nigeria which involves a single contract for surveys, deliveries, installation or construction, assess and charge that person on a fair and reasonable percentage of the contract.²⁶

7.0. BASIS FOR COMPUTING ASSESSABLE INCOME

Except as provided in this section, the income of any individual for each year of assessment from each source of his income (hereinafter referred to as assessable income) shall be the amount of the income of the year immediately preceding the year of assessment from each such source, notwithstanding that he may have ceased to possess that source or that the source may have ceased to produce income.²⁷

Where the relevant tax authority is satisfied that an individual makes, or intends to make up the accounts of a trade, business, profession or vocation carried on by him to some day other than the thirty first day of December, it shall direct that the assessable income from that source be computed on the amount of the gains or profits of the year ending on that day in the year preceding the year of assessment.²⁸

Where the assessable income of an individual from a trade, business, profession or vocation has been computed by reference to an account made up to a certain day, and that individual fails to make up an account to the corresponding day in the year following, the assessable income from that source both for the year of assessment in which the failure occurs and for the two years of assessment next following shall be computed on such basis as the relevant tax authority in its discretion thinks fit.²⁹

Any basis adopted by a relevant tax authority under this section shall be subject to confirmation or amendment by the Board, with or without retrospective effect, if the individual is deemed to

26 Section 7 (a-b) PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

27 Section 23 (1) PITA Supra

28 Section 23 (2) PITA Supra

29 Section 23 (3) PITA Supra

be resident in more than one territory for those three years of assessment, and such additional assessments, reductions or repayments shall be made so as to give effect to any determination of the Board under this subsection.³⁰

8.0. ASSESSMENT IN RELATION TO NEW TRADES

The assessable income of an individual from a trade, business, profession or vocation carried on by him in Nigeria for the year of assessment in which he commenced to carry on the trade, business, profession or vocation in Nigeria and for the two following years of assessment (which years are in this subsection respectively referred to as the first year, the second year, and the third year) shall be ascertained in accordance with the following provision:³¹

(a) for the first year the assessable income shall be the amount of the income of that year;

(b) for the second year the assessable income shall, unless such notice as hereinafter

mentioned is given, be the amount of the income of one year from the date of the commencement in Nigeria of the trade, business, profession or vocation;

(c) for the third year the assessable income shall, unless such notice as is hereinafter mentioned be given, be computed in accordance with the provisions of section 23 (1) of this Act;³²

(d) the individual carrying on the trade, business, profession or vocation shall be entitled, on giving notice in writing to the relevant tax authority within two years after the end of the second year, to require that the assessable income both for the second year and the third year (but not for one or other only of those years) shall be the income of the respective years of assessment:

Provided that he may, by notice in writing given to the relevant tax authority within twelve months after the end of the third year, revoke the notice, and in such case the assessable income both for the second year and the third year shall be computed as if the first notice had never been given;

(e) where such a notice as aforesaid has been given or revoked, such additional assessment, or, on a claim being made for the purpose in writing, such reductions of assessments or repayments of tax shall be made as may be necessary to give effect to paragraph (d) of this subsection.³³

30 Section 23 (4) PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

31 Section 24 (1) PITA Supra

32 Section 24 (1) (a-c) PITA Supra

33 Section 24 (1) (d-e) PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

9.0. AVOIDANCE OF DOUBLE TAXATION AGREEMENT

Where the Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria has entered into agreement with the Government of any country outside Nigeria with a view to affording relief from double taxation in relation to tax imposed under the provisions of this Act, any tax of a similar character imposed by the laws of that country, and that it is expedient that the agreement have effect, the Agreement shall have effect upon ratification by the National Assembly.³⁴

Where Agreements have effect by virtue of this section, any obligation as to secrecy in this Act or in any law of a territory subject to or incorporating the provisions of this Act shall not prevent the disclosure to an authorised officer of the government with which the agreements are made of such information as is required to be disclosed under the Agreements.³⁵

1.0. RETURNS BY TAXABLE PERSON

For each year of assessment, a taxable person shall, without notice or demand therefor, file a return of income in the prescribed form and containing the prescribed information with the tax authority of the State in which the taxable person is deemed to be a resident together with a true and correct statement in writing containing-³⁶

- (a) the amount of income from every source of the year preceding the year of assessment computed in accordance with the provisions of this Act and rules or regulations made thereunder; and
- (b) such particulars as by the return may be required for the purpose of this Act and rules or regulations made thereunder with respect to any such income, allowance, relief, deduction or otherwise as may be material for that purpose.³⁷

The form of return shall contain a declaration which shall be by or on behalf of the taxable person that the return contains a true and correct statement of the income computed in accordance with the provisions of this Act and rules or regulations made thereunder or that particulars given in the return are true and complete.³⁸

34 Section 38 (1) PITA Supra

35 Section 38 (2) PITA Supra

36 Section 41 (1) PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

37 Section 41 (1) (a-b) PITA Supra

38 Subsection 2 of 41 PITA Supra

A taxable person shall file with the relevant tax authority the returns as stipulated in this section within 90 days from the commencement of every year of assessment.³⁹

(4) A written return, statement or an information affecting the liability to tax of an individual for a year of assessment made or given by a person to a tax authority may be treated as having been given to another tax authority in the territory of which that individual is deemed to be resident for that year and, if an error or omission in the return, statement or an information constitutes an offence under the income tax law of that other tax authority, proceedings may be taken by that other tax authority in respect of that offence as though the return, statement or information had been made or given to that other tax authority in the first instance.⁴⁰

11.0. ASSESSMENT OF INCOME TAX

The relevant tax authority shall proceed to assess every taxable person chargeable with income tax as soon as may be, after the time allowed to the person for the delivery of the return provided for in section 41 of this Act, or otherwise as it appears to the relevant tax authority practicable to do so.⁴¹

(2) Where a taxable person has delivered a return, the relevant tax authority may-

(a) accept the return and make an assessment accordingly; or

(b) refuse to accept the return and, to the best of its judgement, determine the amount of the assessable, total or chargeable income of that person and make an assessment accordingly.⁴²

Where a taxable person has not delivered a return within the time allowed and the relevant tax authority is of the opinion that tax is chargeable on that person, the relevant tax authority may, according to the best of its judgement, determine the amount of the assessable, total or chargeable income and make an assessment accordingly, but that assessment shall not affect any liability otherwise incurred by such person by reason of his failure or neglect to deliver a return.⁴³

39 Subsection 3 of 41 PITA Supra

40 Subsection 4 of 41 PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

41 Section 54 (1) PITA Supra

42 Subsection 2 (a-b) of 54 PITA Supra

43 Section 54 (3) PITA Supra

Nothing in this section shall prevent the relevant tax authority from making assessment on a taxable person before the expiration of the time within which the person is required to deliver a return or give notice of his income under the provisions of section 41 of this Act, if any officer of the relevant tax authority considers the assessment to be necessary for any reason of urgency.⁴⁴

12.0. CONCLUSION

Looking at the legal regime of personal income tax in Nigeria and its application, it is imperative to note that it is an important means of raising revenue progressively, provided that: a) the threshold exempts poor people; b) there are higher rates for higher income groups; c) all relevant forms of personal income are captured within the PIT regime and compliance maintained; and d) allowances or deductions do not disproportionately benefit higher earners.

12.1 FINDINGS

It is evident that while imposing tax on taxpayers, there will exist inequality such as allowances and deductions based on income tax collected through payroll deductions, which may also work against those whose income is irregular, informal or unrecognised – which is more frequently the case for women than it is for men. In developing countries, women are less likely to be in the labour force, and if they are, they are more likely to be in the informal sector. Also, men who are employed as casual staff in certain organizations tend to face the same problem.

12.2 RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the above, the Act (PITA) should be amended to reflect the following recommendations:

- i.** Ensure appropriate and graduated rates of tax applied to well-designed income bands that result in higher income earners contributing proportionately more in tax.
- ii.** Strengthen progressivity by gradually limiting higher income earners' access to deductions, exemptions and allowances, and by adopting higher tax rates for higher income earners.

44 Section 54 (4) PITA Cap. P8 LFN 2004

- iii.** Annually review PIT thresholds and income brackets as well as the impact of inflation, in order to account for inflation and reinforce progressivity.